

Synthesis, characterization and electrochemical properties of the transition metal (Fe-Zn) complexes of 2,4-di-*tert*-butyl-6-(pyridin-2-ylazo)-phenol ligand

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Herein we report five homoleptic, six-coordinated 3d metal complexes [Fe^{II}(L)₂], **1**; [Co^{III}(L)₂]ClO₄, [**2**]ClO₄; [Ni^{II}(L)₂], **3**; [Cu^{II}(L)₂], **4**; [Zn^{II}(L)₂], **5** containing tridentate anionic azo-aromatic NNO donor ligand 2,4-di-*tert*-butyl-6-(pyridin-2-ylazo)-phenol (HL). The complexes are synthesized from the reactions between hydrated metal perchlorates and the ligand, HL in 1:2 molar ratio in methanol. One-electron oxidation of the iron complex, **1** by iodine resulted in the isolation of respective cationic complex [Fe^{III}(L)₂]₃, [**1**]₃. All these six complexes are characterized by single crystal X-ray diffraction as well as several spectroscopic techniques and magnetic measurements. While complexes **1**, [**2**]ClO₄ and **5** are diamagnetic the other three complexes [**1**]₃, **3** and **4** behave as simple paramagnets. Redox properties of both HL and metal complexes are studied by cyclic voltammetry. Analysis of three-dimensional X-ray structure together with ⁵⁷Fe Mössbauer spectrum for **1** established a low-spin bis-ligated Fe^{II} configuration. The oxidized iron complex [**1**]₃ displayed a metal centered axial EPR signal at $g_{\perp} = 1.995$ and $g_{\parallel} = 1.993$ and its Mössbauer spectrum together with magnetic moment established a low-spin Fe^{III} configuration revealing that redox events in case of iron are metal centered. One electron reduction of the Co-complex, [**2**]ClO₄ produced a Co^I-complex, which showed 8-lines EPR spectrum at $g_{av.} = 1.997$.

Keywords: Transition metal complexes, redox non-innocence, 2,4-di-*tert*-butyl-6-(pyridin-2-ylazo)-phenol, X-ray crystallography, electrochemistry.

Introduction

The study of redox non-innocent behavior of coordinated ligands in transition metal complexes¹ is an important field for the development of new precursor complexes for bringing about chemical transformation². The physical and chemical properties of these complexes are modulated by varying the ligand framework which allow us to design of molecules with specific characteristics or goals³. The redox-active ligands having energetically accessible levels can change their redox state which in turn facilitate the catalytic activities of such metal complexes⁴. Furthermore organic ligand radicals coordinated to a transition metal ion are the most promising candidates for redox-responsive switching processes⁵ and can be considered as the key player for enzymatic function in metalloenzymes⁶, organic transformations^{2,7} and small molecule activation⁸.

Redox non-innocence of azoaromatic ligands are prima-

rily attributed to the presence of low lying π^* orbital that can accept one or more electron(s) and exhibit various oxidation states as a dominant electron sink in their metal complexes^{9,10} and thus capable of triggering chemical transformation reaction by reductive cleavage¹¹ ($4e^-$ transfer) of azo function *vis-à-vis* metathesis reactions¹². As a part of our recent research activities in metal-coordinated radicals^{13,14}, we have synthesized potentially redox active anionic tridentate N,N,O donor ligand 2,4-di-*tert*-butyl-6-(pyridin-2-ylazo)-phenol (HL) having the combination of two redox active site, e.g. electron-rich phenolate (1-) unit that can donate electron-density to the metal-ion and the azo group which can withdraw electron-density in its low lying π^* orbital. The ligand belongs to the family of a well known dye pyridylazonaphthol (PAN), whose use in analytical chemistry has been known since long¹⁵ and its coordination chemistry is also available in the literature¹⁶. We have previously reported the structure

and electronic properties of molybdenum and chromium complexes of the deprotonated ligand, $[L]^-$ in which the Cr complex is shown to exhibit ligand centered redox events¹⁴. This ligand HL also has close resemblance to 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-phenanthrol (PAPL) reported earlier^{17,18} and the redox non-innocence character as well as the coordination chemistry of PAPL are established by Lemaire *et al.* in recent times^{19,20}. However redox behavior of PAPL upon coordination to transition metal ions is appreciably different than that of HL.

The primary objective of this work is to explore the coordination chemistry of 2,4-di-*tert*-butyl-6-(pyridin-2-ylazo)-phenol (HL) with different 3d-metal ions. Herein we report the synthesis, structural characterization, and investigation of electronic structural properties of newly synthesized transition metal (Fe, Co, Ni, Cu and Zn) complexes of HL, through a series of spectroscopic techniques, magnetic measurements and single crystal X-ray diffraction studies.

Experimental

Materials

The perchlorate salts $M(ClO_4)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ ($M = Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn$) were Aldrich reagents. The ligand HL was prepared by following a reported procedure²¹. Tetrabutylammonium perchlorate, $[Bu_4N]ClO_4$ was prepared and recrystallized as reported earlier²². *Caution! Perchlorates have to be handled with care and appropriate safety precautions!* All other chemicals and solvents were of reagent grade and were used as received.

Physical measurements

Unless otherwise stated syntheses of the complexes were made in open atmosphere. UV-Vis absorption spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Lambda 950 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Infrared and NMR spectra were obtained using a Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer and a Bruker Avance 300/400/500 MHz spectrometer, respectively and $SiMe_4$ was used as the internal standard. A Perkin-Elmer 240C elemental analyzer was used to collect microanalytical data (C, H, N). ESI mass spectra were recorded on a micromass Q-TOF mass spectrometer (Serial no. YA263). Voltammetric measurements were performed under nitrogen atmosphere using a Ag/AgCl reference electrode, with a Pt disk working electrode and a Pt wire auxiliary electrode, in dichloromethane

containing 0.1 M $[Bu_4N]ClO_4$ in a PC-controlled PAR model 273A electrochemistry system. A Pt wire gauge working electrode was used for exhaustive electrolyses. $E_{1/2}$ for the ferrocenium-ferrocene couple under our experimental conditions was 0.40 V. Room temperature magnetic moment measurements for $[1]_3$, **3** and **4** were carried out with Gouy balance (Sherwood Scientific, Cambridge, UK). The experimental magnetic susceptibility data were corrected for underlying diamagnetism using Pascal's tabulated constants. EPR spectra in the X band were recorded at 120 K with a JEOL JES-FA200 spectrometer.

*Synthesis of $[Fe^II(L)_2]$, **1**:* A mixture of 2,4-di-*tert*-butyl-6-(pyridin-2-ylazo)-phenol (HL) (170 mg, 0.55 mmol) and $Fe(ClO_4)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (100 mg, 0.27 mmol) in methanol (40 mL) was refluxed in air for 3 h. The solution gradually became dark violet. Evaporation of this solution afforded a dark solid, which was then crystallized by slow evaporation of its solution in dichloromethane-hexane (2:1) solvent mixture.

Yield: 82%. Anal. Calcd. for $C_{38}H_{48}FeN_6O_2$: C, 67.45; H, 7.15; N, 12.42. Found: C, 65.33; H, 7.20; N, 12.54. ESI-MS: m/z 677.01 $[1+H]^+$; 1H NMR (400 MHz; $CDCl_3$) δ ppm: 8.51 (s, 1H), 7.67 (d, 1H, $J = 8.0$ Hz), 7.37 (t, 1H, $J = 7.8$ Hz), 7.20 (s, 1H), 6.73 (d, 1H, $J = 5.6$ Hz), 6.49 (t, 1H, $J = 6.40$ Hz), 1.49 (s- CH_3 , 9H), 0.89 (s- CH_3 , 9H); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 1597 $[v(C=N) + v(C=C)]$, 1245 $[v(N=N)]$.

*Synthesis of $[Co^III(L)_2]ClO_4$, **[2]** ClO_4 ; $[Ni^II(L)_2]$, **3**; $[Cu^II(L)_2]$, **4**; $[Zn^II(L)_2]$, **5**:* The compounds **[2]** ClO_4 and **3-5** were prepared following an identical synthetic procedure as described above and using the respective metal perchlorate precursors in appropriate 1:2 metal to ligand molar ratio. Complex **[2]** ClO_4 is bright green in colour with 90% yield. All the three complexes **3**, **4** and **5** are blue in colour with greater than 90% yield. Suitable X-ray quality crystals of these complexes were obtained by slow evaporation of their solution in dichloromethane-hexane (2:1) solvent mixture.

[2] ClO_4 : Yield: 90%. Anal. Calcd. for $C_{38}H_{48}CoN_6O_2$: C, 67.14; H, 7.12; N, 12.36. Found: C, 68.63; H, 6.98; N, 12.15. ESI-MS: m/z 679.07 **[2]** $^+$; 1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ ppm: 8.06–8.05 (s + d, 2H), 7.92 (s, 1H), 7.62 (d, 1H, $J = 5.6$ Hz), 8.06–8.05 (m, 2H), 1.41 (s- CH_3 , 9H), 1.05 (s- CH_3 , 9H); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 1602 $[v(C=N) + v(C=C)]$, 1396 $[v(N=N)]$.

3: Yield: >90%. Anal. Calcd. for $C_{38}H_{48}NiN_6O_2$: C, 67.17;

H, 7.12; N, 12.37. Found: C, 68.88; H, 7.26; N, 12.14. ESI-MS: m/z 679.31 [**3**+H]⁺; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 1600 [ν (C=N) + ν (C=C)], 1355 [ν (N=N)].

4: Yield: >90%. Anal. Calcd. for C₃₈H₄₈CuN₆O₂: C, 66.69; H, 7.07; N, 12.28. Found: C, 65.02; H, 7.23; N, 12.51. ESI-MS: m/z 684.26 [**4**+H]⁺; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 1595 [ν (C=N) + ν (C=C)], 1357 [ν (N=N)].

5: Yield: >90%. Anal. Calcd. for C₃₈H₄₈ZnN₆O₂: C, 66.51; H, 7.05; N, 12.25. Found: C, 67.94; H, 7.11; N, 11.89. ESI-MS: m/z 685.02 [**5**+H]⁺; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ ppm: 7.90 (t, 1H, J = 7.5 Hz), 7.70 (d, 1H, J = 8.0 Hz), 7.68 (s, 1H), 7.64 (d, 1H, J = 4.5 Hz), 7.42 (s, 1H), 7.10 (t, 1H, J = 6.5 Hz), 1.32 (s-CH₃, 9H), 1.22 (s-CH₃, 9H); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 1599 [ν (C=N) + ν (C=C)], 1358 [ν (N=N)].

*Synthesis of [Fe^{III}(L)₂]₃, [**1**]₃*: To a dichloromethane solution of the iron complex **1** (50 mg (0.074 mmol) in 15 mL of dichloromethane) a solution of iodine in the same solvent (40 mg in 5 mL) was added drop wise with constant stirring. The solution gradually became blackish green. On solvent evaporation a dark mass was obtained, which was thoroughly washed with hexane to remove excess iodine. The crude product was purified through crystallization by the slow evaporation of its solution in dichloromethane-hexane (2:1) solvent mixture with almost quantitative yield.

Anal. Calcd. for C₃₈H₄₈FeN₆O₂I₃: C, 43.16; H, 4.58; N, 7.95. Found: C, 44.33; H, 4.52; N, 7.79; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 1608 [ν (C=N) + ν (C=C)], 1373 [ν (N=N)].

X-Ray crystallography

Crystallographic data for the compounds **1-5** are collected in Table S1. Suitable X-ray-quality crystals of these compounds are obtained by the slow evaporation of a dichloromethane-hexane solution of the respective compounds. All data were collected on a Bruker SMART APEX-II diffractometer, equipped with graphite-monochromated Mo K α radiation (λ = 0.71073 Å) and were corrected for Lorentz polarization effects. Unfortunately, the data sets for compound [**2**]ClO₄, **3-5** are incomplete in terms of the range of 2θ used in the refinements; the molecular structures, nevertheless, present no unusual features and have been determined unambiguously. Our attempts to grow better crystals were unsuccessful. The routine SQUEEZE was applied to intensity data of the complexes **1** and **5** to consider the disordered

solvent molecules. The number of electrons found in the solvent accessible void is close to that expected for hexane molecule in the unit cell.

1: A total of 26786 reflections were collected, of which 4155 were unique (R_{int} = 0.042), satisfying the $I > 2\sigma(I)$ criterion, and were used in subsequent analysis.

[**1**]₃: A total of 61590 reflections were collected, of which 10555 were unique (R_{int} = 0.062).

[**2**]ClO₄: A total of 34013 reflections were collected, of which 9535 were unique (R_{int} = 0.075).

3: A total of 25957 reflections were collected, of which 3437 were unique (R_{int} = 0.108).

4: A total of 13588 reflections were collected, of which 3215 were unique (R_{int} = 0.028).

5: A total of 13613 reflections were collected, of which 2265 were unique (R_{int} = 0.040).

The structures were solved by employing the SHELXS-97 program package²³ and were refined by full-matrix least squares based on F^2 (SHELXL-97)²⁴. All hydrogen atoms were added in calculated positions.

Results and discussion

The anionic tridentate ligand HL, (HL = 2,4-di-*tert*-butyl-6-(pyridin-2-ylazo)-phenol) was prepared following a reported procedure²¹ by the condensation of 3,5-di-*tert*-butyl benzoquinone with 2-hydrazinopyridine in presence of HClO₄. The ligand exerts three different kinds of coordination, viz. strongly σ donating pyridyl-N and hydroxo-O (after deprotonation) and π -accepting azo-N. Line drawing of the ligand and the isolated metal complexes are summarized in Scheme 1.

The reaction between M(ClO₄)₂.6H₂O (M = Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn) and ligand, HL in 1:2 molar ratio in methanol readily produced intensely blue colored metal complexes of composition [ML₂]ⁿ (n = 0 for **1**, **3-5** and n = 1 for **2**) in almost quantitative yields (>90%). The Electrospray ionization mass spectrometry (ESI-MS) spectra of these isolated complexes corroborates with the formulation as [ML₂]ⁿ (n = 0 for **1**, **3-5** and n = 1 for [**2**]⁺): for example, complexes **1-5** showed intense peaks due to the molecular ions at m/z 677 amu ([**1**]⁺), m/z 679 amu ([**2**]⁺), m/z 679 amu ([**3**+H]⁺), m/z 684 amu ([**4**]⁺) and m/z 685 amu ([**5**]⁺) respectively. The isotopic distribu-

Scheme 1

tion of the complexes correspond very well to the simulations; the spectra are submitted as Figs. S1-S5 in the Supporting information. One-electron oxidation of **1** by iodine in a dichloromethane solvent produced the cationic complex $[1]I_3$ in nearly quantitative yield (Scheme 1). The complex **2** was generated from $[2]^+$ by addition of dilute methanolic solution of hydrazine. The reduced complex is however highly air sensitive and revert back to $[2]^+$ quickly.

X-Ray crystallography

All the six complexes **1**, $[1]I_3$, $[2]ClO_4$, **3-5** form suitable crystals, whose structures have been solved by single-crystal X-ray diffraction studies. Oak Ridge thermal-ellipsoid plot (ORTEP) and atom numbering schemes of the above complexes are shown in Fig. 1. Crystallographic details and the key bond lengths are collected in Tables S1 and S2 respectively.

All the complexes are distorted octahedral and the ligand binds as anion (as NNO donor) via deprotonation of OH group. The complexes **1**, **4** and **5** have crystallographic C_2 symmetry (noncrystallographic D_{2d} symmetry with an S_4 axis) that makes half of the molecule identical to the other half. Among them the $M-N_{py}$ and $M-N_{azo}$ distances are long in the Zn complex, **5** ($d_{Zn1-N1} = 2.216 \text{ \AA}$ and $d_{Zn1-N3} = 2.073 \text{ \AA}$ respectively) due to least metal-ligand interactions. The N=N bond distance of azo group in above complexes ranges from 1.287 to 1.309 \AA indicating appreciable double bond character. Shortest $M-N_{azo}$ distance (1.842 \AA) and longest N=N distance (1.309 \AA) in the Fe complex, **1** may be attributed to the strong $d\pi(Fe)-p\pi(\text{ligand})$ interaction. The Cu-complex, **4** exhibits significantly longer Cu-O bond, 2.136 \AA establishing

maximum distortion, while the M-O bond in complex **1**, **3** and **5** are approximately of the same length. C-O bond in each complex is significantly longer than the C=O double bond distances (1.237(3) \AA). The one-electron-oxidized complex $[1]I_3$ also formed suitable crystal for determination of its three dimensional structure. ORTEP representations with atom numbering schemes of this complex are displayed in Fig. 1. Coordination geometries of the oxidized complexes are similar to those of the neutral analogues ML_2 . The most notable difference between the neutral **1** and cationic $[1]I_3$ species is the significant contraction of the average N=N distances ($\sim 0.023 \text{ \AA}$) and Fe1-O1 distances ($\sim 0.09 \text{ \AA}$). Co-complex $[2]ClO_4$ exerts similar trend that of $[1]^+$ with $d_{N-N(av)}: 1.278 \text{ \AA}$ and $d_{Co-O}: 1.891 \text{ \AA}$.

NMR spectroscopy, Mössbauer spectroscopy and magnetic moment

The complexes **1**, $[2]ClO_4$, and **5** are all diamagnetic and display resolved 1H NMR spectra. A representative 1H NMR spectrum of **1** in $CDCl_3$ along with possible proton assignment is shown in Fig. 2 and the spectra of $[2]ClO_4$ and **5** are submitted at Supporting information (SI; Figs. S6 and S7). In the 1H NMR spectrum of **1**, all six aromatic proton resonances for one ligand are visible in the range δ 8.5–6.4 ppm indicating the presence of high symmetry in solution.

Complexes $[1]I_3$, **3** and **4** are paramagnetic in nature. Room temperature magnetic moment measurements for these complexes were carried out with a Gouy balance. The magnetic moments (μ_{eff}) of $[1]I_3$, **3** and **4** at room temperature are as follows: $[1]I_3$ $\mu_{eff} = 1.70 \mu_B$ indicates the presence of one unpaired electron with $S = 1/2$; **3** $\mu_{eff} = 2.84 \mu_B$

Fig. 1. ORTEPs of the complexes 1-5 and $[1]_3$ at 30% ellipsoid probability. The hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity.

indicating the presence of two unpaired electron with $S = 1$ and $4 \mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.72 \mu_{\text{B}}$ indicates $S = 1/2$ state.

The electronic structures of **1** and $[1]_3$ were further authenticated by zero-field ^{57}Fe Mössbauer spectroscopy (Fig. 3). The spectrum of **1** at 80 K shows a doublet with isomer shift $\delta = 0.17$ mm/s and quadrupole splitting $\Delta E_{\text{Q}} = 0.41$ mm/s. These values are consistent with the presence of low-spin Fe^{II} 25,26 in a distorted octahedral environment. For $[1]_3$ the Mössbauer parameters are $\delta = 0.00$ mm/s and $\Delta E_{\text{Q}} = 3.12$ mm/s and the much larger quadrupole splitting ΔE_{Q} , which is expected for low-spin iron(III), suggests that the iron(III) ion is in its low-spin d^5 configuration 26 . The low absorption at 80 K is due to presence of I_3^- ion in the complex.

Cyclic voltammetry and EPR

Cyclic voltammograms (CV) of the ligand HL were recorded in CH_3CN solutions containing 0.1 (M) TEAP as a supporting electrolyte using platinum as the working electrode at 25°C, the CV-measurements of the metal complexes **1**, $[2]\text{ClO}_4$ and **3-5** were recorded in dichloromethane solutions using tetrabutylammonium perchlorate (TBAP) as the supporting electrolyte. The potentials are referenced to the Ag/AgCl electrode and the results are summarized in Table 1. The voltammograms are displayed in Figs. 4–7.

The ligand showed one irreversible cathodic response at -0.94 V and one reversible electron transfer process at -1.57 V which are due to successive reduction of azo-chro-

Fig. 2. ^1H NMR spectrum of the complex **1** in CDCl_3 solvent (*solvent). Inset: aromatic proton resonances.

Fig. 3. Zero-field ^{57}Fe Mössbauer spectra of **1** (left) and $[\mathbf{1}]_3$ (right).

mophore (Fig. 4). The iron complex **1** showed a reversible anodic response at 0.45 V and a quasi-reversible cathodic response at -0.86 V as shown in Fig. 5. The one-electron redox processes were confirmed by constant-potential electrolysis for the reversible waves at 0.80 V. The redox potential of the oxidation process is low, allowing us to isolate the cationic complex $[\mathbf{1}]^+$ in a crystalline pure state using I_2 as the oxidizing agent. The oxidized iron complex $[\mathbf{1}]_3$ showed an axial EPR spectrum (Fig. 5, inset) at $g_{\perp} = 1.995$ and $g_{\parallel} = 1.993$ clearly suggesting that the oxidation in complex **1** occurs at the Fe^{II} ion. The cobalt complex $[\mathbf{2}]\text{ClO}_4$ showed two

reductive response at -0.14 V and -0.76 V respectively (Fig. 6). We are unable to isolate the complex **2** in solid crystalline form however the reduced complex showed 8-lines EPR spectrum at $g = 1.997$ (Fig. 6, inset). The redox event in case of complexes **1** and $[\mathbf{2}]^+$ is metal centered that is completely different than that of Cr complex where the redox process occurred at the coordinated ligands¹⁴. Complex **3** showed two reductive responses, one at -1.07 V (reversible) another at -1.46 V (irreversible) due to reduction of the coordinated ligands with one reversible oxidative electron transfer process at 0.84 V as shown in Fig. 7. The Cu-com-

Table 1. Selected electrochemical and UV-Vis spectral data

Compound	Cyclic voltammometric data ^a $E_{1/2}^b$, V (ΔE_p , mV)	UV-Vis ^e λ_{max} $f(\epsilon, 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1})$
L	-0.94 ^d , -1.57 (0.14)	–
1	0.45 (0.9), -0.86 ^c	740 (1.44), 610 (1.18), 520 (1.95), 445 ^g , 385 (2.11)
[1] ₃	–	745 ^g , 520 (1.22), 385 (2.6), 295 (3.33)
[2] ClO ₄	-0.14 (0.06), -0.76 (0.065)	720 ^g , 655 (1.8), 460 ^g , 400 (4.6)
3	0.84 (0.09), -1.07 (0.09), -1.45 ^d	635 ^g , 595 (2.53), 550 ^g , 390 (2.0)
4	1.32 ^d , 0.80 ^d , -0.76 (0.14)	595 (1.92), 400 (1.2), 320 (1.15)
5	1.12 ^d , -1.59 (0.14), -0.94 ^d	580 (1.44), 385 (1.12)

^aFor HL acetonitrile solution (supporting electrolyte [Et₄N]ClO₄), rest dichloromethane solution (supporting electrolyte [Bu₄N]ClO₄), working electrode platinum, reference electrode Ag/AgCl, solute concentration ca. 10⁻³ M. ^b $E_{1/2} = 0.5 (E_{\text{pa}} + E_{\text{pc}})$ where E_{pa} and E_{pc} are anodic and cathodic peak potentials respectively, $\Delta E_p = E_{\text{pa}} - E_{\text{pc}}$, scan rate 50 mV s⁻¹. ^cQuasi-reversible. ^dIrreversible. The potential corresponds to E_{pc} . ^eWavelength in nanometer. ^fMolar extinction coefficient in M⁻¹ cm⁻¹ in dichloromethane solvent. ^gBroad shoulder.

Fig. 5. Cyclic voltammogram of complex **1** in dichloromethane. Inset: X-band EPR spectrum of [**1**]⁺ in dichloromethane solution at 120 K.

plex, **4** displayed two irreversible oxidative responses at 0.80 V and 1.32 V and one reversible cathodic response at -0.76

V (Fig. 7). The redox behavior of the Zn-complex **5** is similar to that of the free ligand.

UV-Vis absorption spectroscopy

All the complexes are intensely colored. Electronic spectra of the complexes **1**, [**1**]₃, [**2**]**ClO**₄ and **3-5** are displayed in the Fig. 8 and the data are summarized in Table 1. The complex **1** showed intense transition at 740 nm due to intraligand charge transfer bands (ILCT), a broad absorption at 610 nm and two sharp peaks at 520 and 385 nm along with a shoulder at 445 nm. Oxidized iron complex [**1**]₃ showed a broad absorption at 520 nm along with two sharp peaks at 385 and 295 nm. For complex [**2**]**ClO**₄ an intense transition was noted at 520 nm with two shoulders at 720 and 460 nm along with a sharp peak 400 nm. Two absorption maxima at

Fig. 7. Cyclic voltammogram of complex 3, 4, 5 (from left to right respectively) in dichloromethane.

Fig. 8. Electronic spectra of the complexes 1, $[1]I_3$, $[2]ClO_4$ and 3-5 in dichloromethane.

595 and 390 nm and two shoulders at 635 and 550 nm were observed for the complex 3. The Cu-complex 4 showed three peaks at 595 (sharp), 400 and 320 nm while for complex 5 an intense transition was noted at 580 nm due to intraligand charge transfer along with a sharp peak at 385 nm.

Summary

This work is an attempt to investigate the coordination chemistry of a tri-dentate azo-aromatic ligand 2,4-di-*tert*-butyl-6-(pyridin-2-ylazo)-phenol. This ligand has both donor and acceptor behavior and stabilizes metal ions in their low oxidation states. Five homoleptic, six-coordinated 3d metal complexes of this ligand have been isolated and characterized with the general formula $[M(L)_2]^n$ ($M = Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn$) ($n = 0$ or 1). One-electron oxidation of the iron complex by iodine produced the cationic complex $[1]I_3$. Their molecular and electronic structures are scrutinized thoroughly. The as-

signment of redox site in the complexes is established by using host of physical measurements. The ligand stabilized both the +2 and +3 oxidation states of the metal ions in their coordinated complexes.

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Supporting information

Supporting tables and figures. CCDC Numbers 1849677-1849682 contain the supplementary crystallographic data (CIF).

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